

Ethovision: Locomotor

Setting up Video Analysis

- Click “New,” “Name,” then “Ok”
- Go to “Experiment Settings”
 - Number of subjects: 1
 - Tracked Features: center-point detection
- Go to “Arena Settings 1” → “Arena Settings 1” → then click “Browse” and open the video
- Once you open the video, click “Grab”
- If 1. If “Draw Scale to Calibrate” is selected: draw length of scalebar → type 25 (cm) → OK
- Select 2. Select “Shape and Draw Arena” → select Create Closed Polyline button on top bar
 - Click in each corner of the bottom of the behavior chamber and double click last corner to outline arena
- Select “Zone Group 1”, click the “add subdivided rectangle” button, outline the bottom of the chamber
 - 3 rows by 3 columns → OK
 - In menu on right, right click and delete S1 → S9 **except S5**
- Click 4. Validate setup → OK
- Rename “Arena Settings 1” to the number of the mouse in the video
- Go to “Trial Control Settings 1”
 - Delete “In Zone (1)” and click box next to “Time” condition; change label to “Start” → OK
 - Go to “Settings” for “Start” and under condition is met: After: _____ (enter # of seconds in video until the mouse is in the arena and no person is in the field of view) → OK
 - Click from gray middle of Rule Begin to Condition (Start) to connect boxes with arrow. Repeat for Condition → Action.
 - Settings “Time (1)” condition to “Stop”
 - Under condition is met: After: _____ (enter 20 minutes) → OK
- Rename “Trial Control Settings 1” to the number of the mouse in the video
- Go to “Detection Settings”
 - Detection Settings 1 → Automated Setup → pause when mouse is elongated and draw box from base of tail to tip of nose → Yes
 - Rename Detection Settings 1 to animal ID#
 - Click Save to save the file

Repeat for all other animals:

- Click on previous Animal ID under Arena Settings (1): right click → duplicate → name as next Animal ID
- Click Grab Background Image Button in bottom right → Find video → Grab → adjust Arena and center boxes together and adjust the scale bar as needed → delete and redraw the scale bar if necessary
- Click 4. Validate Setup

- Under Trial Settings (1) and Detection Settings (1) duplicate and name with next Animal ID and adjust settings for that animal's video. (*adjust the delay under Start and outline animal*)

Generating Data from Video Analysis

Once all animals for that study are complete

- Go to “Trial List”
 - Add variable animal ID
 - Add trials and fill in table
- Go to “Acquisition”
 - Track all planned trials
- Click “Analysis Profile 1”
 - Under Location → click the box next to “In zone” → select S5 (only)
 - Trial Statistics: Frequency + Cumulative Duration + Latency to First + Cumulative Duration (%)
 - Add → right click “In zone” and rename to “Center”
- Results → Statistics and Charts → Calculate → Export Data